

Control and Real-Time Analytics

Learner name: Szymon Fudala

Student number: 3170607

Lecturer name: John McDonough

Assignment Title: Comparative Analysis of Real-Time Measurement Techniques in Pharmaceutical Manufacturing: Infra-Red Spectroscopy and Mass Spectroscopy

Principles and Operation of Infra-Red (IR) Spectroscopy and Mass Spectrometry (MS)

Infrared (IR) spectroscopy is a widely used analytical technique that examines the interaction between infrared radiation and matter. As described by (Stuart, 2004, p.2), this method relies on the absorption of infrared radiation by molecules, leading to vibrational transitions within molecular bonds. According to (Cross, 1969, p.10), the process begins with an IR radiation source emitting radiation across the infrared spectrum. A monochromator disperses this radiation, selecting a narrow frequency range before it passes through the sample. Specific molecular vibrations absorb energy at characteristic frequencies, and a detector measures the remaining radiation that has passed through the sample. This energy is then converted into an electrical signal, amplified, and recorded to generate an IR spectrum. The resulting spectrum, which represents absorbance or transmittance as a function of frequency or wavenumber, is analysed to identify functional groups and determine molecular structures. An IR spectrophotometer typically consists of three main components: a radiation source, a monochromator, and a detector.

Historically, dispersive instruments have been used to obtain infrared spectra since the 1940s. However, technological advancements have led to the widespread adoption of Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) over traditional dispersive techniques. As noted by (Stuart, 2004, p.15), FTIR has significantly improved the acquisition of infrared spectra. This technique operates based on radiation interference between two beams, producing an interferogram – a signal that varies with changes in the path length between the beams. The interferogram is then mathematically converted using Fourier transformation to generate a spectrum. Additionally, polarised IR radiation enables the structural study of crystalline solids and fibres. Researchers can gain valuable insights into their molecular structures by analysing changes in the intensity of characteristic absorption bands when polarised radiation interacts with these materials.

On the other hand, mass spectrometry (MS) is a powerful analytical technique used to identify, quantify, and investigate molecular structures based on their mass-to-charge ratio (m/z). (Watson and Sparkman, 2007) describe MS as a method that directly determines the nominal mass and, in some cases, molar mass. The operation of a mass spectrometer involves several key steps. First, the sample undergoes ionisation, fragmenting molecules into charged particles. These ions are then separated in an analyser based on their m/z ratio. Next, they pass through a mass analyser and are detected by a detector, which converts the ion stream into an electrical signal. The strength of this signal is proportional to the number of ions detected. Finally, a computer system processes the data to generate a mass spectrum, which displays signal intensity as a function of the m/z ratio. This spectrum enables the identification and quantification of sample components.

One of the significant advantages of mass spectrometry is its versatility in ionisation techniques, such as electron ionisation (EI), electrospray ionisation (ESI), and matrix-assisted laser desorption/ionisation (MALDI).

Each method offers unique benefits depending on the type of sample and the desired analysis. MS is often coupled with chromatographic techniques, such as gas chromatography (GC-MS) and liquid chromatography (LC-MS), to enhance the separation and identification of complex mixtures. This combination allows for more comprehensive analysis, particularly in pharmaceutical applications, where precise molecular characterisation is essential.

Significant Differences Between Infra-Red Spectroscopy and Mass Spectroscopy

Infrared (IR) Spectroscopy and Mass Spectrometry (MS) are widely used analytical techniques for identifying and characterising chemical compounds. Although both methods are essential tools in analytical chemistry, they operate on fundamentally different principles and provide distinct types of information. Even with a basic understanding of these techniques, it is clear that they function in entirely different ways and, as a result, offer different insights. Below, I discuss three key differences between these methods and their implications in analytical applications. According to (Wade, 2010, chap.12):

1. Principle of Operation

Infrared Spectroscopy (IR) measures the absorption of infrared radiation by molecules, which excites vibrational modes within chemical bonds. The absorbed frequencies are characteristic of specific functional groups, allowing for their identification.

In contrast, Mass Spectrometry (MS) operates by ionising molecules and analysing their mass-to-charge ratio (m/z). Molecular ions and their fragments are separated based on their mass, providing precise molecular weight data and insights into molecular structure.

2. Measurement Scope and Information Provided

IR Spectroscopy primarily provides structural information about molecules, particularly by identifying functional groups based on their vibrational signatures. It is a powerful tool for detecting molecular connectivity and distinguishing between similar compounds.

Conversely, MS is more precise in determining molecular mass and can infer structural details through fragmentation patterns. By analysing the mass spectrum, chemists can deduce the molecular formula and even predict how atoms are connected within a compound.

3. Sample Preparation and Destructive Nature

A key difference between IR and MS is the state and preparation of the sample. IR Spectroscopy can analyse solid, liquid, or gaseous samples with minimal preparation, making it a relatively non-destructive technique.

However, MS requires ionised samples, often destroying the molecules during analysis. While MS provides highly detailed data, the original sample is consumed.

Infrared Spectroscopy and Mass Spectrometry serve complementary roles in analytical chemistry. IR Spectroscopy is ideal for identifying functional groups and understanding molecular connectivity, whereas MS excels in determining molecular mass and analysing complex mixtures. The choice of technique depends on the specific analytical requirements, whether for qualitative structural analysis or precise molecular weight determination.

Common Operational Principles and Analytical Outcomes of Infra-Red Spectroscopy and Mass Spectroscopy

Infrared spectroscopy (IR) and mass spectrometry (MS) are widely used analytical techniques that provide crucial information on the structure and composition of chemical compounds. Both methods are essential in the pharmaceutical and chemical industries and research laboratories, enabling precise analysis of various samples.

A common feature of both techniques is the need for sample preparation before analysis. Although the preparation procedures differ, both require only a tiny sample, minimising material loss. IR spectroscopy typically analyses samples in solid, liquid, or gaseous form with minimal preparation, while MS often involves ionisation and fragmentation of molecules to facilitate detection.

Both IR and MS generate characteristic spectra that allow for the identification of chemical compounds by comparing the obtained data with reference databases. However, the nature of these spectra differs: IR measures the vibrational transitions of molecular bonds, while MS determines the mass-to-charge ratio of ionised molecules. Despite this difference, both techniques provide valuable structural information about the analysed substances.

“These spectroscopic techniques are complementary, and they are most powerful when used together. In many cases, an unknown compound cannot be completely identified from one spectrum without additional information, yet the structure can be determined with confidence using two or more different types of spectra.”(Wade, 2010, p.511)

Additionally, both methods are essential quality control tools in the pharmaceutical and chemical industries. Their high sensitivity and accuracy enable the rapid detection of impurities, contaminants, and variations in chemical composition, ensuring product consistency and regulatory compliance.

In summary, infrared spectroscopy (IR) and mass spectrometry (MS) share several key features that make them indispensable analytical tools. Both require prior sample preparation, utilise spectral analysis for substance identification, and play a crucial role in quality control and scientific research. While their underlying principles differ, they are often used complementarily to provide a more comprehensive understanding of chemical compounds.

Schematic Drawing of Continuous Flow Operation

To determine the optimal locations for installing Infrared Spectroscopy (IR) and Mass Spectrometry (MS) in the continuous tablet production process, it is essential to understand the fundamental principles of these analytical methods. While mastering the advanced aspects of chemistry, physics, and biology underlying these techniques would require extensive specialised knowledge, their general principles can be simplified.

IR spectroscopy works by analysing the interaction of infrared radiation with a sample, allowing for the identification of its composition based on characteristic absorption bands. On the other hand, mass spectrometry (MS) involves ionising sample molecules, analysing their mass in an electromagnetic field, and comparing the results with reference standards. Both methods are highly efficient, and their real-time application enables continuous production process monitoring.

Due to their high precision and rapid analysis capabilities, IR and MS can be strategically implemented at various stages of the production line to monitor critical process parameters (CPPs) and ensure compliance with the final product's critical quality attributes (CQAs). The following sections will outline the key points in the manufacturing process where these analytical methods offer the greatest benefits.

References

Cross, A.D. (1969) *An Introduction to Practical Infra-Red Spectroscopy*. 3rd ed. New York, NY: Springer.

Stuart, B. (2004) *Infrared Spectroscopy: Fundamentals and Applications*. Chichester: J.Wiley & Sons.

Wade, L.G. (2010) *Organic Chemistry*. 7th ed. Upper Saddle River, NJ: Pearson Prentice Hall.

Watson, J.T. and Sparkman, O.D. (2007) *Introduction to Mass Spectrometry: Instrumentation, Applications, and Strategies for Data Interpretation*. 4th ed. Hoboken (N.J.): J. Wiley & Sons.